

Prophylactic Effect of Aqueous and Methanolic extracts of *Andrographis Paniculata* on *Trypanosoma Brucei Brucei* infected mice

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Abstract

The prospect of immunization against the African trypanosomiasis appears remote due to its phenomenal antigenic variation. It is therefore necessary to search for new and more potent anti-trypanosomal compounds of natural origin to complement the existing synthetic anti-trypanosomal drugs that are gradually becoming less potent against the pathogenic trypanosomes. *Andrographis paniculata*; a medicinal plant in Asian has been tested *in-vitro* to have anti-trypanosomal activity. This study aimed at evaluating the prophylactic activity of aqueous and methanolic extract of *Andrographis paniculata* in *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* infected mice. Thirty six (36) male swiss mice of average weight 25g were grouped into six (6) groups of six (6) animals each. Groups (A-D) were orally administered 5000mg/Kg of methanolic leaf, methanolic stem, aqueous leaf and aqueous stem extract of *A. paniculata* respectively while group E (infected) and F were the positive control and negative control group respectively. Animals were inoculated with 10^2 trypanosomes intraperitoneally after 10 days of extract administration. The parasite growth, survival rate, rectal temperature, body weight, PCV and white blood cell differential count were monitored. High parasitic replication was observed in the positive control group with 100% mortality on the 10th day post infection. Some treated mice survived beyond 17 days post infection with no appearance of parasite. Treatment with aqueous leaf extract had the highest survival rate (67%) and aqueous stem extract had the least rate (33%). The rectal temperature showed no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in all treated groups when compared with the negative control. Mean body weight of group A and D showed no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) compared to the negative control group while groups B, C and the positive control showed significant difference. Treated mice maintained stable PCV but there was a reduction in the negative control. The negative control group revealed an increase in lymphocyte and monocyte count compared with the positive control. No significant difference in monocyte and neutrophil count in the treated groups when compared with the positive control ($P < 0.05$). *A. paniculata* leaf and stem contain bioactive components that exhibited trypanocidal activity. The active principles can be isolated for the development of cheap, safe and effective drugs for the treatment and management of African trypanosomiasis.

Keywords: *Andrographis paniculata*; *Trypanosoma brucei brucei*; parasitaemia; trypanocidal activity; prophylactic.

INTRODUCTION

African trypanosomiasis is a disease known as sleeping sickness in humans and 'Nagana' in cattle. It is a disease that invaded Africa by transmission of trypanosomes (causative agents) through biting of tsetse flies [1, 2]. Trypanosomes are flagellate protozoans that inhabit the blood plasma, the lymph and various tissues of their host thereby causing many immune system disorders [3, 4]. Trypanosomes affecting humans include *T. b. gambiense* in West and Central Africa and *T. b. rhodesiense* in East Africa [5]. *T. brucei*, *T. congolense*, *T. vivax*, *T. evansi* are some established trypanosomes affecting animals [6]. African animal trypanosomiasis (AAT) is considered to be the principal disease that limits livestock productivity in sub-Saharan Africa [7].

Human African Trypanosomiasis (HAT) is a challenging and deadly complex disease due to its complex epidemiology and clinical presentations. Currently, there is no vaccine against sleeping sickness due to the ever-changing variable surface glycoproteins (VSG) which prevent effectiveness of the host's immune response [1, 8]. The drugs used for treatment of human and animal trypanosomiasis are limited [9]. Trypanosomes have shown

resistance to current drugs used for the treatment of trypanosomiasis [10]. Ethnobotanical records of various plants indicate promising results using active medicinal plants in the development of cheaper, less toxic drugs [11]. Also, studies have shown that some medicinal plants have anti-trypanosomal activity [12, 13].

Andrographis paniculata used in this study has been effectively used in Asia as medicines for centuries [14]. It is an erect annual herb extremely bitter in taste in all parts of the plant body; thus it is literally known as "**king of bitters**". *Andrographis paniculata* belongs to the *Acanthaceae* family of the plant kingdom and exhibits bioactive components with multifunctional medicinal properties such as activity against fever, annular ulcer, cancer, diabetes, snakebite, inflammation, microbial and parasitic infections to many few [15, 16]. *A. paniculata* is a known native plant in India and Sri Lanka and also distributed in different regions of Southeast Asia, China, America, West Indies and Christmas Island [17].

Documented report on phytochemical screening of *A. paniculata* established the presence of phenols,

saponins, tannins and sugar in leaf and stem of the plant using water and ethanol as solvent [18]. It was also reported that the predominant active compound present in *A. paniculata* is diterpenoid Lactone andrographolide [19]. Akbar [14] reported that LD₅₀ of *A. paniculata* is too high to be determined. This study aimed at evaluating the prophylactic activity of aqueous and methanolic extract of *Andrographis paniculata* in *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* infected mice.

Materials and Methods

Plant Materials

Plants materials were obtained from a garden at Kaduna, Nigeria. Herbs were cut into small pieces and air dried in an open space before blended in food blender to powder form. The plant was authenticated using Dave's garden plant identification forum [20]

Preparation of plant extracts

200g herb powder of the plant leaf and stem was weigh and macerated into 1200ml and 800ml of methanol respectively for 72 hours with occasional shaking. For the aqueous extraction of the plant, 200g herb powder of plant leaf and stem was weigh and macerated in to 1600ml and 1200ml of distilled water for 24hours. Methanolic mixture was filtered with cheese cloth then concentrated using soxhlet extractor. Crude extracts were kept in glass vials on laboratory bench until need.

Experimental Animals

Thirty six (36) male swiss mice of average weight 25g were obtained from Animal House, Nigerian Institute for Trypanosomiasis Research (NITR), Kaduna, Nigeria. Ethical approval was obtained from Animal Unit of the institute with adherence to the animal care guides. The animals were randomly distributed into six (6) groups of six (6) animals each (Group A: methanolic leaf; group B: methanolic stem; group C: aqueous leaf; group D: aqueous stem; group E: positive control and group F: negative control). The animals were housed in standard mice cages with 13hrs/11hrs light/dark photo-period, maintained on standard pellet diet (Vital Plc, Jos, Nigeria) and water *ad libitum*.

Trypanosome

Trypanosoma brucei brucei (Federe strain) was obtained from Nigerian Institute for Trypanosomiasis Research (NITR), Kaduna, Nigeria and inoculated intraperitoneally into two mice before inoculation into the experimental animals after 72hrs. Infected blood collection was done via

cardiac puncture with a heparinized syringe from highly parastiemic mice and immediately diluted with physiological saline to serve as inoculum. 0.1ml of diluted blood was inoculated intraperitoneally into each animal with approximately 10² trypanosomes. This was estimated using the rapid matching method of Herbert and Lumsden [21].

Clinical Examination

All the animals were periodically examined for parasitaemia after inoculation alongside with rectal temperature, body weight, pack cell volume (PCV) and differential white blood cell count.

Crude Extract Administration

Extract from different parts of the plant were dissolved in distilled water to have a concentration of 5000mg/kg body weight. Each animal in the test groups was administered 5000mg/Kg body weight via oral route using gavage and properly observed for 10days before inoculation of parasite.

Statistical Analysis

The group mean ±SEM was calculated for each analyte and between mean evaluated by analysis of variance (ANOVA), post-test analysis was done using Newman-Keuls comparisons. Values of P<0.05 were considered as statistically significance. All statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism software package (version 5).

RESULTS

Clinical signs: There was no clinical change or death record after administered 5000mg/kg body weight of crude extracts of *A. paniculata* for 10days. All the infected mice developed clinical sings of trypanosomiasis which include dullness, slight weight loss, fever and death of some animals.

Parasitaemia: Parasite appears in some animals on 3rd day post infection (3dpi) with fluctuation within each group. High parasitic replication was observed in group E (untreated) compared with the extract groups (Table 1). Also, there was 100% mortality in group E on 10th day post infection with 50%, 17%, 33% and 67% mortality in group A, B, C, and D respectively. Table 2 shows that some treated animals survived beyond 17 days of infection (A = 50%, B = 50%, C = 67% and D = 33%).

Temperature: There was a gradual increase of the mean rectal temperature of the infected mice on 3rd day post infection (Table 3). Slight decrease in temperature of treated mice was observed on 10th dpi and no significant difference ($P<0.05$) observed

when compared with control group on 17th dpi. The peak temperature recorded was 39.7°C in group B. **Weight:** Mean weight of group A and D showed no significant difference ($P<0.05$) compared to control group on 10th dpi while group B, C and untreated showed significant difference. Treated mice maintained stable PCV but there was significant reduction in untreated group (Table 4).

Pack Cell Volume (PCV): Treated animals were able to maintain stable PCV values throughout the study.

There was significant difference ($P<0.05$) in the mean PCV values of untreated animals compared with control group (Table 5)

Haematological Indices: Haematological analysis of the untreated animals showed a drastic increase lymphocyte and monocyte count and decreased neutrophil. However, Table 6 shows that there was no significant difference ($P<0.05$) in monocyte count of the treated animals (group A, B, C, D) with a slight decrease in lymphocyte and neutrophil.

Table 1: Post Infection Parasitemia

	3 Days Post Infection			5 Days Post Infection			10 Days Post Infection			17 Days Post Infection		
	Initial No. of Mice	Average Parasitemia (10 ⁶)	Parasitemia in each group	Initial No. of Mice	Average Parasitemia (10 ⁶)	Parasitemia in each group	Initial No. of Mice	Average Parasitemia (10 ⁶)	Parasitemia in each group	Initial No. of Mice	Average Parasitemia (10 ⁶)	Parasitemia in each group
Methanolic leaf extract	6	2.5	1/6	6	5.4	1/6	6	-	-	6	-	-
Methanolic stem extract	6	0	0/6	6	5.9	2/6	6	77.5	3/6	6	-	-
Aqueous leaf extract	6	3.8	2/6	6	9.1	2/6	6	-	-	6	-	-
Aqueous stem extract	6	5.7	2/6	6	12.5	3/6	6	-	-	6	-	-
Positive Control	6	1.7	6/6	6	19.7	6/6	6	Dead	Dead	6	Dead	Dead

Table 2: Comparative Percentage of survivors of the untreated group and plant extract groups after infection

	3 Days Post Infection			5 Days Post Infection			10 Days Post Infection			17 Days Post Infection		
	Initial No. of Mice	Survival Rate	Mortality Rate (%)	Initial No. of Mice	Survival Rate	Mortality Rate (%)	Initial No. of Mice	Survival Rate	Mortality Rate (%)	Initial No. of Mice	Survival Rate	Mortality Rate (%)
Methanolic leaf extract	6	6/6	0	6	6/6	0	6	3/6	50	6	3/6	50
Methanolic stem extract	6	6/6	0	6	6/6	0	6	1/6	17	6	3/6	50
Aqueous leaf extract	6	6/6	0	6	6/6	0	6	4/6	33	6	4/6	33
Aqueous stem extract	6	6/6	0	6	6/6	0	6	2/6	67	6	2/6	67
Positive Control	6	6/6	0	6	6/6	0	6	0/6	100	6	0/6	100

Table 3: Mean \pm SEM Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C) of Uninfected, infected and treated mice

	3 rd day post Infection	5 th day post Infection	10 th day post Infection	17 th day post Infection
Methanolic leaf extract	38.37 \pm 0.666 ^b	39.03 \pm 0.272 ^b	38.83 \pm 0.338 ^b	38.23 \pm 0.338 ^a
Methanolic stem extract	39.40 \pm 0.115 ^d	39.73 \pm 0.218 ^b	38.37 \pm 0.371 ^b	38.50 \pm 0.450 ^a
Aqueous leaf extract	37.77 \pm 0.497 ^a	39.00 \pm 0.152 ^b	38.23 \pm 0.881 ^a	38.47 \pm 0.233 ^a
Aqueous stem extract	37.73 \pm 0.120 ^a	38.87 \pm 0.881 ^b	38.30 \pm 0.152 ^b	38.10 \pm 0.208 ^a
Positive Control	38.90 \pm 0.240 ^c	39.30 \pm 0.208 ^b	Dead	Dead
Negative Control	37.30 \pm 0.577 ^a	37.26 \pm 0.145 ^a	37.07 \pm 0.145 ^a	37.70 \pm 0.057 ^a

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=6. Values with different superscripts along a column are significantly different at $P<0.05$

Table 4: Mean \pm SEM Weight (g) of Uninfected, infected and treated mice

	3 rd day post Infection	5 th day post Infection	10 th day post Infection	17 th day post Infection
Methanolic leaf extract	29.50 \pm 0.346 ^a	28.80 \pm 0.328 ^a	28.60 \pm 0.057 ^b	28.76 \pm 0.881 ^a
Methanolic stem extract	29.26 \pm 0.666 ^b	29.00 \pm 0.185 ^b	28.80 \pm 0.317 ^c	28.86 \pm 0.392 ^c
Aqueous leaf extract	29.20 \pm 0.366 ^b	28.85 \pm 0.384 ^a	28.50 \pm 0.317 ^b	28.75 \pm 0.417 ^b
Aqueous stem extract	29.18 \pm 0.550 ^a	29.00 \pm 0.328 ^a	28.40 \pm 0.577 ^b	28.65 \pm 0.491 ^a
Positive Control	29.00 \pm 0.917 ^c	27.86 \pm 0.982 ^c	Dead	Dead
Negative Control	29.56 \pm 0.133 ^a	30.20 \pm 0.404 ^a	30.66 \pm 0.392 ^a	30.90 \pm 0.458 ^a

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=6. Values with different superscripts along a column are significantly different at $P<0.05$

Table 5: Mean \pm SEM Pack cell volume (%) of Uninfected, infected and treated mice

	1 st Week post infection	2 nd Week post infection	3 rd Week post infection
Methanolic leaf extract	42.66 \pm 0.666 ^a	42.66 \pm 0.881 ^b	42.66 \pm 0.881 ^b
Methanolic stem extract	41.00 \pm 0.577 ^a	41.66 \pm 0.201 ^b	42.66 \pm 0.201 ^b
Aqueous leaf extract	42.33 \pm 0.066 ^a	42.66 \pm 0.333 ^b	45.00 \pm 0.577 ^a
Aqueous stem extract	42.00 \pm 0.527 ^a	42.66 \pm 0.201 ^b	46.33 \pm 0.333 ^a
Positive Control	40.66 \pm 0.201 ^b	40.33 \pm 0.333 ^b	Dead
Negative Control	44.66 \pm 0.666 ^a	46.33 \pm 0.881 ^a	47.33 \pm 0.333 ^a

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=6. Values with different superscripts along a column are significantly different at $P<0.05$

Table 6: Mean \pm SEM Haematological Indices of Uninfected, infected and treated mice

	Neutrophil	Lymphocyte	Monocyte
Methanolic leaf extract	86.33 \pm 0.238 ^b	9.77 \pm 0.822 ^b	3.77 \pm 1.638 ^a
Methanolic stem extract	85.33 \pm 0.876 ^b	11.66 \pm 0.618 ^b	2.99 \pm 1.261 ^a
Aqueous leaf extract	88.77 \pm 0.722 ^b	7.60 \pm 0.464 ^b	3.55 \pm 1.283 ^a
Aqueous stem extract	88.99 \pm 0.638 ^b	7.22 \pm 0.007 ^a	3.77 \pm 1.638 ^a
Positive Control	25.00 \pm 0.120 ^c	44.50 \pm 0.350 ^c	7.50 \pm 0.500 ^b
Negative Control (Group F)	97.22 \pm 0.220 ^a	1.55 \pm 0.110 ^a	1.33 \pm 0.001 ^a

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=6. Values with different superscripts along a column are significantly different at $P < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

Safety is the most important consideration for the assessment of any agent which is administered for the treatment of disease. No record of mortality after the administration of 5000mg/kg body weight. This is in agreement with Akbar [14] which reported that LD₅₀ of *A. paniculata* is too high to be determined and no pathological change after administering higher dose of andrographolide which is the predominant component of *A. paniculata* is in agreement with the observation. Atawodi *et al.* [22] reported that complete elimination, reduction of parasite or increase in survival rate of animals treated with plant extract could be agreed as index of anti-trypanosomal activity. It was observed in this study that both crude methanolic and aqueous extracts obtained from leaf and stem of *A. paniculata* exhibit prophylactic activity. This activity can be traceable to nicotin-induced inhibition of mitochondrial electron complexes and resultant increase in nitric oxide (NO) in different parts of the brain by treatment with aqueous and ethanol extracts of *A. paniculata* [23]. Decrease in parasitaemia supported Dua *et al.* [24] which reported that xanthenes from the root of *A. paniculata* exhibited promising anti-protzoal activity.

Survival of some animals treated with *A. paniculata* extracts could be the ability of the plant to accelerate activities of antioxidant enzymes (superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxide) that reduced oxidative reaction by the free radicals [25, 26, 27]. Anand *et al.* [18] reported that both aqueous and ethanol extracts of *A. paniculata* leaf and stem contain saponins and tannins; these bioactive components possess wide spectrum of anti-trypanosomal activity and their mechanism of action

is thought to be via interaction with parasite membrane sterols, protein and phospholipids thereby lyses the parasitic cells [28, 29, 30].

All clinical observations during this study established trypanosome effect on the infected animals which characterized by fluctuating temperature and parasitaemia. However, stability in temperature was observed on 10th and 17th day post infection in animals treated with extracts; this could be as a result of immunosuppressive capacity derived from the extracts [15, 31]. Despite the administration of extracts, there was loss of weight which may be traceable to impaired nutrient absorption due to the ability of the extracts to form complex with some essential nutrients and make them unavailable [32, 33]. Anaemia is a sign of trypanosome infection which involves in pack cell volume (PCV) of individual. The low PCV observed in the infected untreated animals could be as a result of acute haemolysis due to replication of the trypanosomes thus increase the susceptibility of red blood cell membrane to oxidative damage probably as a result of depletion of antioxidant enzymes [4, 34, 35, 36]. In contrast, stable PCV observed in treated group may be traceable to extracts ability to inhibit trypanosome replication thus reduced the severity of anaemia that usually reflects the intensity and duration of parasitaemia in any animal [37, 38, 39]. It could also due to the antioxidant effects of the plant extract on liver defense, causing an increase in activities of catalase, superoxide dismutase and glutathione-S-transferase enzymes and reduced lactate dehydrogenase activity [40, 41].

Leucocytosis and lymphocytosis observed in untreated group may be attributed to the host action

against the infection which may be as a result of wax and wear syndrome on the animal immune system caused by the ever changing variable surface glycoprotein (VSG) of the trypanosome [6, 42, 43]. However, decrease in neutrophils count could be as a result of overwhelming animals immune system by the trypanosomes or secondary bacterial infection associated with trypanosomiasis [43, 44].

CONCLUSION

Andrographis paniculata is a promising medicinal plant that is significant in a healthy society. *A. paniculata* leaf and stem contain bioactive components that exhibited trypanocidal activity which can be isolated for the development of cheap, safe and effective drugs for the treatment and management of African trypanosomiasis. There is a need to isolate and characterize the active compound(s) in the plant so as to maximize the medicinal properties of *A. paniculata*

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest among the authors.

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**NIGERIAN INSTITUTE FOR TRYPANOSOMIASIS RESEARCH
(FEDERAL MINISTRY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY)
P.M.B. 2077, KADUNA, KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA**

Ref: ARAF/04/15 Date: 1st June, 2015

ANIMAL CARE ETHICAL COMMITTEE APPROVAL

Animal care ethical committee (ACEC) of the above named institute hereby approve the use of Mice for the research study titled Prophylactic effect of Aqueous and Methanolic Extracts of Andrographis paniculata on Trypanosoma brucei brucei infected mice

This approval was issued after thorough examination of the information provided on the Animal Research Application Form.

Thank you.

A circular blue ink stamp from the Nigerian Institute for Trypanosomiasis Research. The text around the perimeter reads 'NIGERIAN INSTITUTE FOR TRYPANOSOMIASIS RESEARCH' and 'RECEIVED'. In the center, there is a handwritten signature and the date '1st June 2015'.
Mr. Kehinde David
For: ACEC, NITR